

Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic and Semi-Magic Squares of Orders 3, 5, 7 and 9

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The work is also available as pdf file at author's sites:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16158>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

This work brings **magic** and **semi-magic** squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 for **reduced entries algebraic**. By **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less numbers. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These **entries** are **non-sequential positive** and **negative** numbers. In some cases, these may be **decimal** or **fractional** values depending on the orders of a magic squares. In this work we bring different ways of writing **magic** and **semi-magic** squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9. These are based on three types of magic squares, i.e., **cornered**, **single-digit bordered** and **double-digit bordered** magic squares, except for the magic square of orders 5 and 7. In some cases, we worked with **pandiagonal** magic squares of orders 5 and 7 for **reduced entries algebraic**. It is not necessary, but we worked with **magic rectangles** with **equal width** and **length** of the same category within a magic square. If we relax this condition, i.e., by considering only equality in width, still we have good results. For more details refer author's work [30]. It is not necessary, but we worked with **magic rectangles** with **equal widths** and **lengths**. of the same category within a magic square. Previously, the author brought similar kind of work [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] for the orders 3 to 12 specially for the for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few **entries** and **days** are the **sums** of magic squares. In this work we worked with much more possibilities rather than previous works.

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1 Introduction

In this paper, the author worked with **magic** and **semi-magic** squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 for the **reduced entries algebraic**. By **reduced** or **less entries** we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square of order n , we are using less numbers. Moreover, the **entries** are no more sequential numbers. These entries are **non-sequential positive** and **negative numbers**. In some cases, these may be **decimal** or **fractional** values depending on the order of a magic square. In this work we bring different ways of writing **magic** and **semi-magic** squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9. These are based on three types of magic squares, i.e., **cornered**, **single-digit bordered** and **double-digit bordered** magic squares, except for the magic square of order 5 and 7. In some cases, we worked with **pandiagonal** magic squares of orders 5 and 7 for **reduced entries algebraic**. It is not necessary, but we worked with **magic rectangles** with **equal widths** and **lengths** of the same category within a magic square. If we relax this condition, i.e., by considering only equality in width, still we have good results. For more details refer author's work [30]. These studied gives us **magic** and **semi-magic** squares. In all the situations, the conditions for **semi-magic** squares to become magic squares are also studied. Combining together we have complete work on **odd orders** magic squares up to order 11. The tables below give the number of **magic** and **semi-magic** squares that we worked for even and odd orders. The work on order 11 magic squares shall be presented separately. For work with **even** orders magic squares from 4 to 12 refer Taneja [36, 37].

Orders	Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Total
3	1	1	2
5	2	1	3
7	5	3	8
9	11	9	20
11	-	-	-

The author [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] also worked on similar kind of work but from different point of view. This work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 12 for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of the magic squares.

2 Magic Square of order 3

Example 2.1. A magic square of order 3 is given by

			15
8	1	6	15
3	5	7	15
4	9	2	15
15	15	15	15

2.1 Reduced Entries Magic and Semi-Magic Squares of Order 3

Result 2.1. A magic square of order 3 with **reduced entries algebraic** is given by

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	$M/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$
A1	A2	M-A1-A2

• Details

Knowing only two entries A1 and A2 and the magic sum M, we can construct a magic square of order 3. The some of the entries are **decimal** numbers. To avoid this we may consider the magic sum as **multiple of 3**. The Result 2.1 shall be used frequently in works on reduced magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9. This magic square can seen in the web-site of F. Gaspalou [3].

Below are two examples. One is with **decimal** entries and another is with magic sums as multiple of 3. These are based on 2.1.

Example 2.2. A magic square of order 3 with reduced entries is given by

	mgc			28
	11	15	2	28
	1/3	9 1/3	18 1/3	28
	16 2/3	3 2/3	7 2/3	28
	28	28	28	28

	mgc			30
	5	16	9	30
	14	10	6	30
	11	4	15	30
	30	30	30	30

The first example is with **decimal** entries because the magic sum is not a multiple of 3. The second example is with integer values as the sum of magic square is a **multiple of 3**.

The magic square of order 3 given in Result 2.1 is with decimal entries except the magic sum multiple of 3. To get normal entries, below is another result giving **reduced entries semi-magic** square of order 3

Result 2.2. A *semi-magic* square of order 3 with **reduced entries algebraic semi-magic** is given by

a1	M-a1-b1	b1
M-a1-a2	a1+a2+b1 +b2-M	M-b1-b2
a2	M-a2-b2	b2

• **Details**

Knowing only four entries a_1 , a_2 , b_1 and b_2 and the magic sum M , we can construct a **semi-magic**. This result is applied in construction **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 given in Result 5.11.

3 Magic Squares of order 5

Example 3.1. Let's consider following three examples of magic square of order 5:

5x5	pan	65	65	65	65	65
65	1	7	13	19	25	65
65	18	24	5	6	12	65
65	10	11	17	23	4	65
65	22	3	9	15	16	65
	14	20	21	2	8	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

5x5	mgc					65
	16	11	12	23	3	65
	9	13	17	25	1	65
	14	15	10	7	19	65
	5	6	22	8	24	65
	21	20	4	2	18	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

5x5	mgc					65
	22	25	5	7	6	65
	2	12	17	10	24	65
	3	11	13	15	23	65
	18	16	9	14	8	65
	20	1	21	19	4	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

The first example is one of the classical example of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. The second one is **cornered** magic square and the third example is **single-digit bordered** magic square.

Based on these three examples we shall work on reduced entries magic squares of order 5.

3.1 Reduced Entries Magic Squares of Order 5

Below are three results with examples of **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares of order 5.

Result 3.1. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	$M/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$A5$	$S-M-A5$
$A1$	$A2$	$M-A1-A2$	$A6$	$S-M-A6$
$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$A4$	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$
$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	$S-M-A4$	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$

• **Details**

It is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there is a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 are of equal width and length. In order to get magic square without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum of magic square of order 3 as multiple of 3. See below two examples.

Example 3.2. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 5 based on the Result 3.1:

1a	mgc					110		1b	mgc						131
	4	27	29	35	15	110			3	29	31	62	6	131	
	45	20	-5	19	31	110			49	21	-7	19	49	131	
	11	13	36	21	29	110			11	13	39	21	47	131	
	27	17	31	25	10	110			18	17	67	34	-5	131	
	23	33	19	10	25	110			50	51	1	-5	34	131	
5x5	110	110	110	110	110	110		5x5	131	131	131	131	131	131	131

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 63$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 151$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 50 \times 75$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 68 \times 102.$$

Result 3.2. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4
A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8
A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7
A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6
S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8

• **Details**

It is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 with reduced entries. This magic square can be seen in the web-site of F. Gaspalou [3]. See below two examples.

Example 3.3. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 5 based on the Result 3.2:

2a	pan	140	140	140	140	140	2b	pan	141	141	141	141	141
140	21	24	38	27	30	140	141	21	24	39	27	30	141
140	57	33	-6	36	20	140	141	57	33	-6	36	21	141
140	9	32	39	63	-3	140	141	9	33	39	63	-3	141
140	45	27	12	5	51	140	141	45	27	12	6	51	141
	8	24	57	9	42	140		9	24	57	9	42	141
5x5	140	140	140	140	140	140	5x5	141	141	141	141	141	141

These are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **even** and **odd** numbers magic sums.

3.2 Reduced Entries Semi-Magic Squares of Order 5

In this case, we have only one result for **semi-magic** square of order 5. A condition to bring it a magic square is also studied.

Result 3.3. *Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:*

A6	$2*M-A9-S+A7$	S-M-A7	S-M-A6	A9
$2*S-3*M+A9-2*A7+A2+A1-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$2*M-S+A4+2*A7-A2-A1-A9$
$2*A7+S-M-A6-A2-A1$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$A6-2*A7+A2+A1$
A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4
$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A9+2*S-3*M-A7$	A7	A6	S-M-A6

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 embedded with a magic square of order 3. It is **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. If we apply the condition $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$ then it becomes magic square, where M and S are the magic sums of the magic squares of order 3 and 5, respectively. Below are two examples.

Example 3.4. *Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 5 based on the Result 3.2:*

a	semi						210	b	mgc	M/3=S/5					150
	16	58	13	14	19	120		16	28	43	44	19	150		
	-36	-7	48	49	66	120		24	-7	48	49	36	150		
	25	86	30	-26	5	120		55	86	30	-26	5	150		
	14	11	12	67	16	120		14	11	12	67	46	150		
	101	-28	17	16	14	120		41	32	17	16	44	150		
5x5	120	120	120	120	120	120	5x5	150	150	150	150	150	150		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{Sm_{5 \times 5}} = 120$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 150$$

The first magic square is **semi-magic**. The second one is magic square as it satisfies the condition $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$.

4 Magic Squares of Order 7

Example 4.1. Let's consider following four examples of magic squares of order 7:

1	pan	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	2	mgc							175	
175	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175			42	38	40	5	4	2	44	175
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175			1	34	37	17	19	18	49	175
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175			3	14	24	29	22	36	47	175
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175			43	15	23	25	27	35	7	175
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175			41	30	28	21	26	20	9	175
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175			39	32	13	33	31	16	11	175
	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175			6	12	10	45	46	48	8	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175			175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175
3	mgc							175	4	mgc								175
	4	30	44	32	15	13	37	175			26	21	28	30	20	8	42	175
	46	20	6	18	35	9	41	175			27	25	23	33	17	12	38	175
	34	16	26	21	28	17	33	175			22	29	24	14	36	48	2	175
	42	8	27	25	23	47	3	175			34	32	31	13	15	45	5	175
	43	7	22	29	24	39	11	175			16	18	19	35	37	10	40	175
	1	49	48	12	19	36	10	175			46	49	7	47	6	11	9	175
	5	45	2	38	31	14	40	175			4	1	43	3	44	41	39	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175			175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

The first example is a **pandiagonal** magic square. The second magic square is **single-digit bordered** magic square embedded with magic squares of orders 5 and 3. The third example is **double-digit bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in its inner part. In this case the four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums. The fourth example is **cornered** magic square having magic squares of orders 3 and 5 at upper-left corner. In this case the each two magic rectangles of order 2×3 and 2×5 are of equal sums.

Based on examples 2, 3 and 4, we shall work with **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares. It is divided in two parts. One when we always have magic squares. The second part is when the results are **semi-magic** squares. In this case, apply conditions to get magic squares.

4.1 Reduced Entries Magic Squares of Order 7

Based on the four examples given in 4.2 we shall bring five different ways to write **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares of order 7. The algebraic structure of these magic square is also presented.

Result 4.1. *Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 7:*

$(T-M)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A10$	$(T-M)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$
A13	A12	$3*(T-M)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$
$A15+A16-(T-M)/4$	$3*(T-M)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(T-M)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-M)/4$
$(T-M)/2-A15$	A15	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A7	$(T-M)/2-A7$
$(T-M)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A8	$(T-M)/2-A8$
$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-M)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*M-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6
$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A4$	$(T-M)/2-A5$	A14+A13-A6	$T-3*M-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$

• Details

*It is **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 embedded with magic square of order 3. The four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for*

order 3 as multiple of 3. The letters *M* and *T* are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 4.2. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 4.1:

1a	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							170	1b	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							181
	18	24	21	20	19	19	49	170		22	24	19	24	23	19	50	181		
	23	22	19	20	21	-9	74	170		23	22	25	20	21	-6	76	181		
	31	9	-7	48	49	25	15	170		29	15	-8	50	51	31	13	181		
	15	25	86	30	-26	17	23	170		19	25	90	31	-28	17	27	181		
	14	26	11	12	67	18	22	170		18	26	11	12	70	18	26	181		
	27	-2	31	14	15	69	16	170		27	1	37	14	15	71	16	181		
	42	66	9	26	25	31	-29	170		43	68	7	30	29	31	-27	181		
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 170$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 93$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 181$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 40 \times 60$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 44 \times 66.$$

Result 4.2. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 7:

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12
A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13
$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	$2*M-S$	$5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14$
$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14
$T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10$	A10	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$
$S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2

• **Details**

It is **cornered** magic square of order 7, where there are magic square of orders 3 and 5 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×3 are of equal width and length in each case. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. The letters M, S and T are magic sums of magic squares of of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 4.3. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 4.2:

2a	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							180	2b	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							191
	4	27	29	35	15	31	39	180		3	29	31	32	16	31	49	191		
	45	20	-5	19	31	33	37	180		49	21	-7	19	29	33	47	191		
	11	13	36	21	29	35	35	180		11	13	39	21	27	35	45	191		
	27	17	31	25	10	39	31	180		28	17	27	24	15	64	16	191		
	23	33	19	10	25	37	33	180		20	31	21	15	24	37	43	191		
	60	25	27	34	29	35	-30	180		68	25	27	51	29	40	-49	191		
	10	45	43	36	41	-30	35	180		12	55	53	29	51	-49	40	191		
	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example	Second Example
$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$	$M_{3 \times 3} = 63$
$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$	$S_{5 \times 5} = 111$
$T_{7 \times 7} = 180$	$T_{7 \times 7} = 191$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example	Second Example
$MR_{2 \times 3} = 50 \times 75$	$MR_{2 \times 3} = 48 \times 72$
$MR_{2 \times 5} = 70 \times 175$	$MR_{2 \times 5} = 80 \times 200.$

Result 4.3. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 7:

A6	2*M-A9-S+A7	S-M-A7	S-M-A6	A9	A14	T-S-A14
2*S-3*M+A9- 2*A7+A2+A1-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	2*M-S+A4+2*A7- A2-A1-A9	A15	T-S-A15
2*A7+S-M-A6- A2-A1	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	A6-2*A7+A2+A1	(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S- A17-A16-A15-A14	(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+ A14+A15+A16+A17
A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16
4*M-2*S-A9	A9+2*S-3*M-A7	A7	A6	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17
T-2*S-A7+A11+ M+A6+A15-A14	A11	A7-(1/2)*S-M- A6+(3/2)*T-A13-A12- 2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T
A7-A11+S-M-A6- A15+A14	T-S-A11	A13+A12+2*A11- A7+M+A6+A15-A14- (1/2)*T-(1/2)*S	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2

• Details

It is **cornered** magic square of order 7, where there is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner embedded with magic square of order 3. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×5 are of equal width and length. In order to get magic square without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum of magic square of order 3 as multiple of 3. The letters M, S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 4.4. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 4.3:

3a	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							150	3b	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							171
	16	58	13	14	19	24	6	150		16	57	14	15	19	24	26	171		
	-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	150		-34	-7	48	49	65	25	25	171		
	25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	150		26	86	30	-26	5	23	27	171		
	14	11	12	67	16	26	4	150		14	11	12	67	17	26	24	171		
	101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	150		99	-26	17	16	15	27	23	171		
	21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	150		40	21	19	22	23	25	21	171		
	9	9	42	8	7	60	15	150		10	29	31	28	27	21	25	171		
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150		171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 120$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 150$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 121$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 171$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 30 \times 50$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 30 \times 50$$

Result 4.4. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 7:

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13
A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14
A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13	3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16
A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15
S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16
T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13	A10	A7+A8+3*(T-S)/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T
A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	(S-T)/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2

• **Details**

It is **cornered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×5 are of equal width and length. Moreover, the magic square of order 5 is **pandiagonal**. The letters *S* and *T* are magic sums of magic squares of of orders 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 4.5. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 4.4:

4a	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							190	4b	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							175
	21	24	38	27	30	57	-7	190		21	24	39	27	30	57	-23	175		
	57	33	-6	36	20	60	-10	190		57	33	-6	36	21	60	-26	175		
	9	32	39	63	-3	-121	171	190		9	33	39	63	-3	-161	195	175		
	45	27	12	5	51	63	-13	190		45	27	12	6	51	63	-29	175		
	8	24	57	9	42	66	-16	190		9	24	57	9	42	66	-32	175		
	20	48	-48	51	54	25	40	190		4	48	-72	51	54	17	73	175		
	30	2	98	-1	-4	40	25	190		30	-14	106	-17	-20	73	17	175		
	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 190$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 141$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 175$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 50 \times 125$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 34 \times 85$$

4.2 Reduced Entries Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 7

Result 4.5. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 7:

$A7+A22+A9+A10+A14+A1+A2+A6+A3+A5-A12-A24-A16$	$A8+A23+A19-A1-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+A4-A5$	A1	A6	$A22-A10+A19+A2-A18-A13+A3$	A15	$2*A24-A8+A16-A7-2*A22-A9-A23-2*A19-A14-A1-2*A2+A18-A6+A17-2*A3-A4$
$A19+A14+A2-A18-A17+A12+A3+2*A4-A5-A7$	$T+A16-A7-A22-A19+A20-A14-A1-2*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A3$	A2	A7	A11	$A7+A22-A19-A20+A1+A6-A12-2*A4+A5-A16$	A19
$T-A9-A10+A23-A14-A1-A15-A6+A12-A3-A5$	$2*A7+2*A22+A9+A19-A20+A14+2*A1+2*A2+A11-A18+A15+2*A6-A12-A13+2*A3-A4+2*A5-2*T-A16$	$A14+A11+A15+A6-A4-A23-A20$	$2*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A23-2*A19-A14-2*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A12-A3-A4$	$A8-A7-A22+A9+A10+A23+A19+A20-A1-A11-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+3*A4-A5$	A16	A20
$T-A22-A23-A19-A20-A21-A2+A18+A15-A12-A4$	$A10-A23-A19+A1+A6-A12+A5$	$T+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-A6-A3-A5$	$A22-A10+A23+2*A19+A14+2*A2+A11-A18-A17+A12+A3+A4-T$	A12	A17	A21
$T-A7-A22+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-2*A6+A12+A13-A3+A4-A5$	$A16-A7-A22+A23+A19+A20+A21-A1-A15-A6+2*A12+A13-A3+2*A4-A5$	A3	A8	$T-A8+A7-A9-A23-2*A19-A20-A14+A1-A2+A18+A15+A6+A17-2*A12-A13-A3-3*A4+A5$	$A7+A22+A9-A23+A19-A20-A21+2*A14+A1+2*A2+A11-A18+A15+2*A6-A17-A12-A13+2*A3+A5-T-A16$	A22
$A7+A22-A23-A20+A14+A1+A2+A11+A15+2*A6-A12-A13+A3-2*A4+2*A5-T$	$A7+A22-A23-A20-A21+A14+A1+A2+A15+A6-A12-A13+A3-A4-A16$	A4	A9	A13	$2*T+A16-2*A7-2*A22-A9+A23+2*A20+A21-2*A14-2*A1-2*A2-A11-2*A15-3*A6+2*A12+A13-2*A3+2*A4-2*A5$	A23
$A16+A20+A21-A14-A2+A17-A3$	$2*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A10-A19-A14-A1-A2-A6-A3-A4-A5$	A5	A10	A14	A18	$A8-A16+A7+A22+A9+A19-A20-A21+A14+A1+2*A2-A18+A6-A17+2*A3+A4-T$

• Details

It is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7. See below two examples.

Example 4.6. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 4.5:

5a	pan	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	5b	pan	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251
200	-69	45	11	16	15	25	157	200	200	251	-120	45	11	16	15	25	259	251	251
200	41	124	12	17	21	-44	29	200	200	251	41	175	12	17	21	-44	29	251	251
200	112	-193	9	144	72	26	30	200	200	251	163	-295	9	246	72	26	30	251	251
200	50	-22	126	-34	22	27	31	200	200	251	101	-22	177	-85	22	27	31	251	251
200	120	115	13	18	23	-121	32	200	200	251	171	115	13	18	74	-172	32	251	251
200	-119	-29	14	19	23	259	33	200	200	251	-170	-29	14	19	23	361	33	251	251
	65	160	15	20	24	28	-112	200	200		65	262	15	20	24	28	-163	251	251
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

Second Example

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 251.$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers.

4.3 Reduced Entries Semi-Magic Squares of Order 7

In this case, we have three result for **semi-magic** square of order 7. Conditions to bring them as magic squares are also studied.

Result 4.6. *Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 7:*

A15	$(7/2)*T-(9/2)*S-A8+A5-2*M-A11$	A8	$(9/2)*S-A15-A16-A10-A9-A5+2*M-(5/2)*T+A11$	A9	A10	A16
$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A15+A16-A14+2*A8-A5+2*M-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A11-2*A8+A5-2*M+A13+A14-A16+A15$
$A5-(7/2)*S-2*M+(5/2)*T-2*A8$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	$(5/2)*S-(3/2)*T+2*A8-A5+2*M$
A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13
A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	T-S-A14
A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	T-S-A11
$6*S-A16-4*T$	$A11+A8-A5+(7/2)*S+2*M-(5/2)*T$	T-S-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+(7/2)*T-(11/2)*S+A5-2*M-A11$	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15

• **Details**

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 7 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 5. It contains magic square of order 3 at upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal width and length. In order to get magic square without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum of magic square of order 3 as multiple of 3. Moreover, in order to get a magic square of order 7, we must have the condition $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The letters M, S and T are magic sums of magic squares of of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 4.7. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 4.6:

1a	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							260	1b	mgc	S/5=T/7							210
		25	-204	18	276	19	20	26	180			25	-156	18	258	19	20	26	210
		234	-7	48	49	44	6	-194	180			296	-9	52	53	50	4	-236	210
		-241	86	30	-26	15	35	281	180			-213	94	32	-30	15	39	273	210
		23	11	12	67	16	34	17	180			23	11	12	73	16	38	37	210
		24	12	14	49	25	40	16	180			24	10	14	57	27	42	36	210
		21	38	36	1	40	25	19	180			21	44	40	-3	42	27	39	210
		94	244	22	-236	21	20	15	180			34	216	42	-198	41	40	35	210
		180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180			210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example	Second Example
$S_{3 \times 3} = 90$	$S_{3 \times 3} = 96$
$S_{5 \times 5} = 140$	$S_{5 \times 5} = 150$
$T_{Sm7 \times 7} = 180$	$T_{7 \times 7} = 210$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example	Second Example
$MR_{2 \times 3} = 50 \times 75$	$MR_{2 \times 3} = 34 \times 81$

Result 4.7. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 7:

A18	T-S+A11+A15-A14	A11	S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	A19
5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18
A15	3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6	T-S-A15
A16	A5	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-A5	T-S-A16
A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	T-S-A17
A14	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	T-S-A14
6*S-A19-4*T	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 7 embedded with magic squares of orders 5 and 3. In order to get magic square without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum of magic square of order 3 as multiple of 3. Moreover, in order to get a magic square of order 7, we must have two conditions $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$ and $S = \frac{3}{5} \times M$. The letters M, S and T are magic sums of magic squares of of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 4.8. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 4.7:

2a	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							250	2b	mgc	M/3=S/5=T/7							140
	38	82	31	-55	32	33	39	200		38	72	31	-105	32	33	39	140		
	-41	26	34	33	28	29	91	200		-41	26	4	13	28	29	81	140		
	35	44	13	38	39	16	15	200		35	14	23	18	19	26	5	140		
	36	25	56	30	4	35	14	200		36	25	16	20	24	15	4	140		
	37	24	21	22	47	36	13	200		37	24	21	22	17	16	3	140		
	34	31	26	27	32	34	16	200		34	11	36	27	12	14	6	140		
	61	-32	19	105	18	17	12	200		1	-32	9	145	8	7	2	140		
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140		

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the conditions $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$ and $S = \frac{3}{5} \times M$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 150$$

$$T_{Sm_{7 \times 7}} = 200$$

Second Example

$$S_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 100$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 140$$

Result 4.8. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 7:

A17	T-S+A10+A14-A13	A10	S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	A18
A14	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	T-S-A14
5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	5*S-4*T+A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17
A15	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	T-S-A15
A16	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	T-S-A16
A13	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	T-S-A13
6*S-A18-4*T	A13-A10-A14	T-S-A10	A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+A14-2*S+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17

• **Details**

It is **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in the middle. Moreover, in order to get a magic square of order 7, we must have the condition $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The letters S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 4.9. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 4.8:

3a	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							130	3b	mgc	S/5=T/7							196
	62	94	41	-193	44	47	65	160		62	100	41	-163	44	47	65	196		
	53	14	17	36	20	23	-3	160		53	14	17	66	20	23	3	196		
	-75	50	26	-13	29	18	125	160		-75	50	26	-13	29	48	131	196		
	56	2	30	32	56	-10	-6	160		56	2	60	32	56	-10	0	196		
	59	38	20	5	3	44	-9	160		59	38	20	5	33	44	-3	196		
	50	6	17	50	2	35	0	160		50	36	17	50	2	35	6	196		
	-45	-44	9	243	6	3	-12	160		-9	-44	15	219	12	9	-6	196		
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160		196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196		

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the conditions $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{Sm_{7 \times 7}} = 160$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 196$$

5 Magic Squares of Order 9

Example 5.1. Let's consider following 4 magic squares of order 9

9x9	pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	9x9	mgc							369		
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369		69	16	80	12	72	17	21	56	26	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369		13	66	2	70	10	65	61	58	24	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369		73	9	38	34	51	32	50	6	76	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369		68	14	44	48	31	39	43	79	3	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369		11	71	46	36	41	52	30	7	75	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369		78	4	42	40	53	33	37	59	23	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369		19	63	35	47	29	49	45	22	60	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369		20	62	55	25	77	8	67	1	54	369
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369		18	64	27	57	5	74	15	81	28	369
1	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	2	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
9x9	mgc									369	9x9	mgc									369
	38	43	42	50	32	27	55	15	67	369		8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	369
	45	41	37	46	36	62	20	8	74	369		1	58	54	56	21	20	18	60	81	369
	40	39	44	49	33	26	56	80	2	369		3	17	50	53	33	35	34	65	79	369
	34	35	52	31	53	65	17	10	72	369		5	19	30	40	45	38	52	63	77	369
	48	47	30	29	51	23	59	14	68	369		73	59	31	39	41	43	51	23	9	369
	60	54	57	18	58	21	19	77	5	369		71	57	46	44	37	42	36	25	11	369
	22	28	25	64	24	63	61	81	1	369		69	55	48	29	49	47	32	27	13	369
	78	75	16	13	79	76	12	11	9	369		67	22	28	26	61	62	64	24	15	369
	4	7	66	69	3	6	70	73	71	369		72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	369
3	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	4	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

The first magic square is **pandiagonal** magic square, where the blocks of order 3 are equal sums **semi-magic** squares. The second magic square is **double-digit bordered** magic square embedded with magic square of order 5. It has four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×5 . The third magic square is **cornered** magic squares, where the magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 are at upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal width and length for each order. The fourth magic square is **single-digit bordered** magic square. It includes magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7.

More details on these types of magic squares given in Example 5.2 refer author's work [11, 16, 24, 27]. Based on examples 2, 3 and 4 given in 5.2, we shall construct the **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares.

5.1 Reduced Entries Magic Squares of Order 9

Based on the examples 1, 2, 3 and 4 given in 5.2 we shall bring eleven different ways to write **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares of order 9. It is divided in two parts. The first is with magic square of order 3. The second part is with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5, 7 and 9.

5.1.1 With Magic Square of Order 3

Result 5.1. *Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:*

$(S-L)/2+A28+2*A12+A17-A18$	A28	$3*(S-L)/4+A19+A20+A21+A22$	$(L-S)/2-A19$	$(L-S)/2-A20$	$(L-S)/2-A21$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(5*S-L)/4-A28-A12-A17$	$(L-S)/2-A28-A12+A18$
$(9*S-5*L)/4+A17-A23+A12$	$L-S-A28-2*A12-A17+A18$	$5*(L-S)/4-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A19	A20	A21	A22	A28+A12-A18	A23
$3*(S-L)/4+A24+A25+A26+A27$	$5*(L-S)/4-A24-A25-A26-A27$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$5*(L-S)/4-A13-A14-A15-A16$	$3*(S-L)/4+A13+A14+A15+A16$
$(L-S)/2-A24$	A24	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A13	$(L-S)/2-A13$
$(L-S)/2-A25$	A25	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A14	$(L-S)/2-A14$
$(L-S)/2-A26$	A26	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	A15	$(L-S)/2-A15$
$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$
$L-S-A28-2*A12+A18-2*A17+A23$	A12	$5*(L-S)/4-A8-A9-A10-A11$	A8	a21	A10	A11	A17	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A28+A12-A18+A17-A23$
$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A12+A17-A18$	$3*(S-L)/4+A8+A9+A10+A11$	$(L-S)/2-A8$	$(L-S)/2-A9$	$(L-S)/2-A10$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	A18	$(L-S)/2-A17$

• Details

It is **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with **cornered** magic square of order 5 containing magic square of order 3 at upper-left corner. The four magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. To avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The letters M, S and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.2. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.1:

1a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								200	1b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								221
	41	38	62	11	10	9	8	13	8	200		31	38	47	21	20	19	18	9	18	221
	36	-1	-22	29	30	31	32	32	33	200		12	19	3	29	30	31	32	32	33	221
	82	-42	3	28	29	59	1	2	38	200		67	-17	2	30	31	56	2	27	23	221
	6	34	46	20	-6	15	45	23	17	200		16	34	50	21	-8	15	43	23	27	221
	5	35	11	12	37	16	44	24	16	200		15	35	11	12	40	16	42	24	26	221
	4	36	7	14	69	30	0	25	15	200		14	36	8	14	65	29	5	25	25	221
	3	37	53	46	-9	0	30	26	14	200		13	37	50	44	-7	5	29	26	24	221
	5	22	22	18	19	20	21	27	46	200		25	22	47	18	19	20	21	27	22	221
	18	41	18	22	21	20	19	28	13	200		28	17	3	32	31	30	29	28	23	221
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 120$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 63$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 121$$

$$L_{7 \times 7} = 221$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 60 \times 90$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 40 \times 100$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 58 \times 87$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 50 \times 125$$

Result 5.2. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

$(T-M)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A10$	$(T-M)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	A23	L-T-A23
A13	A12	$3*(T-M)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A24	L-T-A24
$A15+A16-(T-M)/4$	$3*(T-M)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(T-M)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-M)/4$	A25	L-T-A25
$(T-M)/2-A15$	A15	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A7	$(T-M)/2-A7$	A26	L-T-A26
$(T-M)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A8	$(T-M)/2-A8$	$7*(L-T)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	$5*(T-L)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$
A14-A6+A9	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-M)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*M-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A27	L-T-A27
$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A4$	$(T-M)/2-A5$	A14+A13-A6	$T-3*M-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A28	L-T-A28
A18	$(5*T-3*M)/2-L+A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23$	A19	A20	$(9*L+3*M)/2-6*T-2*A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A21	A22	$(L-T)/2$	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A18	$2*L+(3*M-7*T)/2-A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$5*T-(7*L+3*M)/2+2*A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23+A19+A20+A21+A22$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	$(L-T)/2$

• Details

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at upper-left having a magic square of order 3 in the middle of it. The four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. Also, the magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums. To avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The letters M, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.3. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.2:

2a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								200	2b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								201
	-13	47	65	-9	-11	37	4	65	15	200		-11	47	64	-7	-9	37	0	65	15	201
	45	43	-35	39	41	26	-39	67	13	200		45	43	-32	39	41	32	-47	67	13	201
	85	-55	24	17	19	-23	53	69	11	200		84	-52	25	15	17	-20	52	69	11	201
	-19	49	15	20	25	33	-3	71	9	200		-17	49	11	19	27	33	-1	71	9	201
	-21	51	21	23	16	35	-5	-140	220	200		-19	51	21	23	13	35	-3	-140	220	201
	53	40	-11	27	29	-49	31	73	7	200		53	46	-8	27	29	-57	31	73	7	201
	-10	-55	41	3	1	61	79	75	5	200		-14	-63	40	5	3	61	89	75	5	201
	55	-77	57	59	62	61	63	40	-120	200		55	-71	57	59	56	61	63	40	-119	201
	25	157	23	21	18	19	17	-120	40	200		25	151	23	21	24	19	17	-119	40	201
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 120$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 57$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 121$$

$$L_{7 \times 7} = 201$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 30 \times 45$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 80 \times 280$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 32 \times 48$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 80 \times 280$$

Result 5.3. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11	A21	L-T-A21
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A22	L-T-A22
A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A23	L-T-A23
$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	$2*M-S$	$5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14$	A24	L-T-A24
$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26$
$T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10$	A10	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	A25	L-T-A25
$S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	A26	L-T-A26
A16	$5*S-4*T-L+A16+2*A13+2*A4+2*A1+2*A21-A22-A1-A2+2*A9+2*A8+2*A5+A10+A14$	A17	A18	$(9*L+T)/2-5*S-2*A16-2*A13-2*A4-2*A12-A21+A22+A1+A2-2*A9-2*A8-2*A5-A10-A14-A17-A18-A19-A20$	A19	A20	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A16	$2*L+3*T-5*S-A16-2*A13-2*A4-2*A12-A21+A22+A1+A2-2*A9-2*A8-2*A5-A10-A14$	L-T-A17	L-T-A18	$5*S-(3*T+7*L)/2+2*A16+2*A13+2*A4+2*A12+A21-A22-A1-A2+2*A9+2*A8+2*A5+A10+A14+A17+A18+A19+A20$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2

• Details

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **cornered** magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner having a magic square of order 5 and 3 again at upper-left corner. Each two magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length in each case. Again, to avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The letters M, S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.4. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.3:

3a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								240
	3	28	29	44	6	21	39	31	39	240
	46	20	-6	15	35	22	38	32	38	240
	11	12	37	16	34	23	37	33	37	240
	12	14	49	25	10	60	0	34	36	240
	38	36	1	10	25	24	36	44	26	240
	29	18	19	64	20	30	-10	35	35	240
	31	42	41	-4	40	-10	30	36	34	240
	26	-102	27	28	207	29	30	35	-40	240
	44	172	43	42	-137	41	40	-40	35	240
	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

3b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								241
	2	30	31	41	7	21	39	31	39	241
	50	21	-8	15	33	22	38	32	38	241
	11	12	40	16	32	23	37	33	37	241
	13	14	45	24	15	60	0	34	36	241
	35	34	3	15	24	24	36	44	26	241
	27	18	19	66	20	30	-9	35	35	241
	33	42	41	-6	40	-9	30	36	34	241
	26	-102	27	28	207	29	30	35	-39	241
	44	172	43	42	-137	41	40	-39	35	241
	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 170$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 240$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 63$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 111$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 171$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 241$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 50 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 60 \times 150$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 70 \times 245$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 48 \times 72$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 60 \times 150$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 70 \times 245$$

Result 5.4. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

A6	2*M-A9-S+A7	S-M-A7	S-M-A6	A9	A14	T-S-A14	2*L-5*T-A24-A7 +2*S+2*A15+2*A11 +2*A12+A17	4*T-L+A24+A7- 2*S-2*A15-2*A11- 2*A12-A17
2*S-3*M+A9- 2*A7+A2+A1-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	2*M-S+A4+2*A7- A2-A1-A9	A15	T-S-A15	L-T-A24	A24
2*A7+S-M-A6- A2-A1	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	A6-2*A7+A2+A1	(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S- A17-A16-A15-A14	(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A14 +A15+A16+A17	L-T-A25	A25
A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16	L-T-A26	A26
4*M-2*S-A9	A9+2*S-3*M-A7	A7	A6	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17	(13*T-7*L)/2 +A26+A25+2*A24+ A28+A27+A7-2*S- 2*A15-2*A11-2*A12- A17	(9*L-15*T)/2-A26- A25-2*A24-A28- A27-A7+2*S +2*A15+2*A11+ 2*A12+A17
T-2*S-A7+A11+ M+A6+A15-A14	A11	A7-(1/2)*S-M- A6+(3/2)*T-A13-A12- 2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	L-T-A27	A27
A7-A11+S-M-A6- A15+A14	T-S-A11	A13+A12+2*A11- A7+M+A6+A15-A14- (1/2)*T-(1/2)*S	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	L-T-A28	A28
A19	A19-2*A16-A13	(7/2)*L-(7/2)*T-A22- A21-A20-A23 +2*A16+A13-2*A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L
L-T-A19	L-T+2*A16+A13- A19	(5/2)*T-(5/2)*L+ A22+A21+A20+A23- 2*A16-A13+2*A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2

• Details

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **cornered** magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 at upper-left corner. It has magic square of order 3 in the middle. Each two magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length in each case. Again, to avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The magic sum of magic square of order 5 may be **semi-magic** but still we have order 9 as a magic square. The letters M, S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.5. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.3:

4a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								200	4b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								261	
	16	58	13	14	19	24	6	2	48	200		16	57	14	15	19	24	6	121	-11	261	
	-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	16	34	200		-34	-7	48	49	65	25	5	76	34	261	
	25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	15	35	200		26	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	75	35	261	
	14	11	12	67	16	26	4	14	36	200		14	11	12	67	17	26	4	74	36	261	
	101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	103	-53	200		99	-26	17	16	15	27	3	-106	216	261	
	21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	13	37	200		20	21	-11	22	23	15	61	73	37	261	
	9	9	42	8	7	60	15	12	38	200		10	9	41	8	7	61	15	72	38	261	
	29	-46	66	30	31	32	33	25	0	200		29	-46	276	30	31	32	33	55	-179	261	
	21	96	-16	20	19	18	17	0	25	200		81	156	-166	80	79	78	77	-179	55	261	
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 120$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 150$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 121$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 151$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 261$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 30 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 50 \times 175$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 30 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 110 \times 385$$

Result 5.5. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

A15	$(7/2)*T-(9/2)*S-A8+A5-2*M-A11$	A8	$(9/2)*S-A15-A16-A10-A9-A5+2*M-(5/2)*T+A11$	A9	A10	A16	A23	L-T-A23
$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A15+A16-A14+2*A8-A5+2*M-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A11-2*A8+A5-2*M+A13+A14-A16+A15$	A24	L-T-A24
$A5-(7/2)*S-2*M+(5/2)*T-2*A8$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	$(5/2)*S-(3/2)*T+2*A8-A5+2*M$	A25	L-T-A25
A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13	A26	L-T-A26
A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	T-S-A14	$7*(L-T)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	$5*(T-L)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$
A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	T-S-A11	A27	L-T-A27
$6*S-A16-4*T$	$A11+A8-A5+(7/2)*S+2*M-(5/2)*T$	T-S-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+(7/2)*T-(11/2)*S+A5-2*M-A11$	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15	A28	L-T-A28
A18	$(5*T-3*M)/2-L+A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*S-A8-A24+A23$	A19	A20	$(9*L+3*M)/2-6*T-2*A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*S+A8+A24-A23-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A21	A22	$(L-T)/2$	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A18	$2*L+(3*M-7*T)/2-A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*S+A8+A24-A23$	L-T-A19	#VALOR!	$5*T-(7*L+3*M)/2+2*A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*S-A8-A24+A23+A19+A20+A21+A22$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	$(L-T)/2$

• Details

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 5. It has magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner of it. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. Again, to avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The magic sum of magic square of order 7 may be **semi-magic** but still we have order 9 as a magic square. The letters M, S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.6. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.5:

5a	pan	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								200	5b	pan	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								211	
	25	-246	18	288	19	20	26	33	17	200		25	-160	18	227	19	20	26	33	3	211	
	194	-7	48	49	23	13	-170	34	16	200		265	-8	50	51	17	15	-215	34	2	211	
	-267	86	30	-26	15	21	291	35	15	200		-207	90	31	-28	15	17	257	35	1	211	
	23	11	12	67	16	20	1	36	14	200		23	11	12	70	16	16	27	36	0	211	
	24	19	14	21	18	54	0	-38	88	200		24	21	14	13	16	61	26	-87	123	211	
	21	17	22	15	54	18	3	37	13	200		21	11	18	19	61	16	29	37	-1	211	
	130	270	6	-264	5	4	-1	38	12	200		24	210	32	-177	31	30	25	38	-2	211	
	28	-223	29	30	248	31	32	25	0	200		28	-174	29	30	150	31	32	18	67	211	
	22	273	21	20	-198	19	18	0	25	200		8	210	7	6	-114	5	4	67	18	211	
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 126$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 150$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 93$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 125$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 175$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 211$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 36 \times 54$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 50 \times 175$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 32 \times 48$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 36 \times 126$$

Result 5.6. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

A18	$T-S+A11+A15-A14$	A11	$S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14$	A12	A13	A19	$L-S-A21+A22-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15+A27-A1$	$S-T+A21-A22+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-A27+A1$
$5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14$	A6	$M-A6-A9-A8+A7$	$S-M-A7$	A8	A9	$5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18$	A27	L-T-A27
A15	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6$	T-S-A15	A28	L-T-A28
A16	A5	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$S-M-A5$	T-S-A16	A29	L-T-A29
A17	A4	A1	A2	$M-A1-A2$	$S-M-A4$	T-S-A17	$(5*L-7*T)/2+A21-A22+S+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-2*A27+A1-A28-A29-A30-A31$	$(5*T-3*L)/2-A21+A22-S-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15+2*A27-A1+A28+A29+A30+A31$
A14	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	$S-M-A8$	$S-M-A6$	T-S-A14	A30	L-T-A30
$6*S-A19-4*T$	$A14-A11-A15$	T-S-A11	$A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14$	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A31	L-T-A31
A21	A22	A23	A24	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	A25	A26	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26$	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2

• Details

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner embedded with a **cornered** magic square of orders 5 and 3. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. Again, to avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The magic sum of magic square of order 7 may be **semi-magic** but still we have order 9 as a magic square. The letters M, S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.7. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.6:

6a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								230
	79	95	51	-242	55	59	83	73	-23	230
	-212	31	12	15	39	43	252	115	-65	230
	67	22	-4	45	49	28	-27	119	-69	230
	71	27	83	30	-23	23	-31	123	-73	230
	75	23	11	15	64	27	-35	-513	563	230
	63	37	38	35	11	19	-23	127	-77	230
	37	-55	-11	282	-15	-19	-39	131	-81	230
	91	95	99	103	-431	107	111	25	30	230
	-41	-45	-49	-53	481	-57	-61	30	25	230
	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230

6b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								321
	79	106	51	-232	55	59	83	154	-34	321
	-167	31	12	25	39	43	218	115	5	321
	67	52	-4	45	49	8	-16	119	1	321
	71	27	83	30	-23	33	-20	123	-3	321
	75	23	11	15	64	37	-24	-349	469	321
	63	17	48	35	21	29	-12	127	-7	321
	13	-55	0	283	-4	-8	-28	131	-11	321
	91	95	99	103	-186	107	111	60	-159	321
	29	25	21	17	306	13	9	-159	60	321
	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 180$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 230$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 150$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 201$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 321$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 50 \times 175$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 120 \times 420$$

5.1.2 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

Result 5.7. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

$(S-L)/2+A30+2*A14+A19-A20$	A30	$3*(S-L)/4+A21+A22+A23+A24$	$(L-S)/2-A21$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(L-S)/2-A23$	$(L-S)/2-A24$	$(5*S-L)/4-A30-A14-A19$	$(L-S)/2-A30-A14+A20$
$(9*S-5*L)/4+A19-A25+A14$	$L-S-A30-2*A14-A19+A20$	$5*(L-S)/4-A21-A22-A23-A24$	A21	A22	A23	A24	A30+A14-A20	A25
$3*(S-L)/4+A26+A27+A28+A29$	$5*(L-S)/4-A26-A27-A28-A29$	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	$5*(L-S)/4-A15-A16-A17-A18$	$3*(S-L)/4+A15+A16+A17+A18$
$(L-S)/2-A26$	A26	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A15	$(L-S)/2-A15$
$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$
$(L-S)/2-A28$	A28	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A17	$(L-S)/2-A17$
$(L-S)/2-A29$	A29	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A18	$(L-S)/2-A18$
$L-S-A30-2*A14+A20-2*A19+A25$	A14	$5*(L-S)/4-A10-A11-A12-A13$	A10	A11	A12	A13	A19	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A30+A14-A20+A19-A25$
$(L-S)/2-A14$	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A14+A19-A20$	$3*(S-L)/4+A10+A11+A12+A13$	$(L-S)/2-A10$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(L-S)/2-A13$	A20	$(L-S)/2-A19$

• Details

It is **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 with embedded with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 at the middle of it. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×5 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The letters S and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 5 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.8. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.7:

7a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									200	7b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT									231
	101	69	156	-11	-13	-15	-17	-53	-17	200		87	69	135	3	1	-1	-3	-57	-3	231		
	45	-61	-116	51	53	55	57	57	59	200		13	-33	-81	51	53	55	57	57	59	231		
	196	-156	11	13	64	15	17	-68	108	200		175	-121	11	13	67	15	17	-33	87	231		
	-21	61	35	19	-7	21	52	39	1	200		-7	61	35	19	-7	21	55	39	15	231		
	-23	63	3	60	23	39	-5	41	-1	200		-9	63	3	63	23	39	-5	41	13	231		
	-25	65	27	15	5	42	31	43	-3	200		-11	65	27	15	5	45	31	43	11	231		
	-27	67	44	13	35	3	25	45	-5	200		-13	67	47	13	35	3	25	45	9	231		
	-49	37	-28	29	31	33	35	47	65	200		-21	37	7	29	31	33	35	47	33	231		
	3	55	68	11	9	7	5	49	-7	200		17	23	47	25	23	21	19	49	7	231		
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231		

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 120$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 123$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 231.$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 40 \times 100$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 54 \times 135.$$

Result 5.8. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	$2*L-5*T-A23-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$	$4*T-L+A23+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$
A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	L-T-A23	A23
A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	$5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13$	$3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16$	L-T-A24	A24
A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15	L-T-A25	A25
S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	$(13*T-7*L)/2+A25+A24+2*A23+A27+A26+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$	$(9*L-15*T)/2-A25-A24-2*A23-A27-A26-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$
T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13	A10	A7+A8+3*(T-S)/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	L-T-A26	A26
A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	(S-T)/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	L-T-A27	A27
A18	A18-2*A15-A12	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A20-A19-A22+2*A15+A12-2*A18$	A19	A20	A21	A22	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L
L-T-A18	L-T+2*A15+A12-A18	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A20+A19+A22-2*A15-A12+2*A18$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2

Example 5.9. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.8:

8a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								220	8b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								231
	11	14	48	17	20	47	-7	118	-48	220		11	14	49	17	20	47	-7	137	-57	231
	47	23	-16	26	30	50	-10	-7	77	220		47	23	-16	26	31	50	-10	3	77	231
	-1	42	29	53	-13	-106	146	-10	80	220		-1	43	29	53	-13	-106	146	0	80	231
	35	17	2	15	41	53	-13	-13	83	220		35	17	2	16	41	53	-13	-3	83	231
	18	14	47	-1	32	56	-16	192	-122	220		19	14	47	-1	32	56	-16	158	-78	231
	20	38	-43	41	44	20	30	-16	86	220		20	38	-43	41	44	20	31	-6	86	231
	20	2	83	-1	-4	30	20	-19	89	220		20	2	83	-1	-4	31	20	-9	89	231
	62	-88	-7	65	68	71	74	35	-60	220		62	-88	28	65	68	71	74	40	-89	231
	8	158	77	5	2	-1	-4	-60	35	220		18	168	52	15	12	9	6	-89	40	231
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 150$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 220$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 111$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 151$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 231$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 40 \times 100$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 70 \times 245$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 40 \times 100$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 80 \times 280$$

• **Details**

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 at upper-left corner. It contains magic square of order 7 also as a **cornered** magic square. The magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length in each case. The letters S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Result 5.9. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

A17	T-S+A10+A14-A13	A10	S-A17-A18-A12-A11- 2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	A18	L-T-A25	A25
A14	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	T-S-A14	L-T-A26	A26
5*T-6*S-A17+A18- A16-A14-A15-A13	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5- A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	5*S-4*T+ A13+A14+A15 +A16-A18+A17	5*(T-L)/2+ A26+A25+A27+ A28+A29+A30	7*(L-T)/2-A26- A25-A27-A28- A29-A30
A15	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	T-S-A15	L-T-A27	A27
A16	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	T-S-A16	L-T-A28	A28
A13	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	T-S-A13	L-T-A29	A29
6*S-A18-4*T	A13-A10-A14	T-S-A10	A17+A18+A12+A11+2 *A10+T-2*S+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	L-T-A30	A30
A20	5*T-A25+A26-A13 +A18+A8-5*S+A7- A14+A10+A20-A16- A15-A17-L	(9*L-17*T)/2-A23-A22- A21-A24+A25-A26+A13- A18-A8+5*S-A7+A14- A10-2*A20+A16+ A15+A17	A21	A22	A23	A24	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L
L-T-A20	2*L-6*T+A25- A26+A13-A18- A8+5*S-A7+A14- A10-A20+ A16+A15+A17	(15*T-7*L)/2+A23+ A22+A21+A24-A25 +A26-A13+A18+A8- 5*S+A7-A14+A10 +2*A20-A16-A15-A17	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2

• Details

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner. It contains **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in the middle. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic sum of magic square of order 7 may be **semi-magic** but still we have order 9 as a magic square. The letters S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.10. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.9:

9a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								220	9b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								251
	63	115	42	-199	45	48	66	-47	87	220		63	116	42	-199	45	48	66	-17	87	251
	54	15	18	32	21	24	16	-50	90	220		54	15	18	32	21	24	17	-20	90	251
	21	51	27	-12	30	14	49	467	-427	220		26	51	27	-12	30	14	45	392	-322	251
	57	3	26	33	57	-9	13	-53	93	220		57	3	26	33	57	-9	14	-23	93	251
	60	39	21	6	-1	45	10	-56	96	220		60	39	21	6	-1	45	11	-26	96	251
	51	2	18	51	3	36	19	-59	99	220		51	2	18	51	3	36	20	-29	99	251
	-126	-45	28	269	25	22	7	-62	102	220		-130	-45	29	270	26	23	8	-32	102	251
	72	97	-347	75	78	81	84	20	60	220		72	71	-216	75	78	81	84	35	-29	251
	-32	-57	387	-35	-38	-41	-44	60	20	220		-2	-1	286	-5	-8	-11	-14	-29	35	251
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 180$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 220$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 181$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 251$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 40 \times 140$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 70 \times 245$$

5.1.3 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 7

Result 5.10. *Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:*

$A7+A22+A9+A10+A14+A1+A2+A6+A3+A5-A12-T-A16$	$A8+A23+A19-A1-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+A4-A5$	A1	A6	$A22-A10+A19+A2-A18-A13+A3$	A15	$2^*T-A8+A16-A7-2^*A22-A9-A23-2^*A19-A14-A1-2^*A2+A18-A6+A17-2^*A3-A4$	A30	L-T-A30
$A19+A14+A2-A18-A17+A12+A3+2^*A4-A5-A7$	$T+A16-A7-A22-A19+A20-A14-A1-2^*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A3$	A2	A7	A11	$A7+A22-A19-A20+A1+A6-A12-2^*A4+A5-A16$	A19	A31	L-T-A31
$T-A9-A10+A23-A14-A1-A15-A6+A12-A3-A5$	$2^*A7+2^*A22+A9+A19-A20+A14+2^*A1+2^*A2+A11-A18+A15+2^*A6-A12-A13+2^*A3-A4+2^*A5-2^*T-A16$	$A14+A11+A15+A6-A4-A23-A20$	$2^*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A23-2^*A19-A14-2^*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A12-A3-A4$	$A8-A7-A22+A9+A10+A23+A19+A20-A1-A11-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+3^*A4-A5$	A16	A20	A32	L-T-A32
$T-A22-A23-A19-A20-A21-A2+A18+A15-A12-A4$	$A10-A23-A19+A1+A6-A12+A5$	$T+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-A6-A3-A5$	$A22-A10+A23+2^*A19+A14+2^*A2+A11-A18-A17+A12+A3+A4-T$	A12	A17	A21	A33	L-T-A33
$T-A7-A22+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-2^*A6+A12+A13-A3+A4-A5$	$A16-A7-A22+A23+A19+A20+A21-A1-A15-A6+2^*A12+A13-A3+2^*A4-A5$	A3	A8	$T-A8+A7-A9-A23-2^*A19-A20-A14+A1-A2+A18+A15+A6+A17-2^*A12-A13-A3-3^*A4+A5$	$A7+A22+A9-A23+A19-A20-A21+2^*A14+A1+2^*A2+A11-A18+A15+2^*A6-A17-A12-A13+2^*A3+A5-T-A16$	A22	A34	L-T-A34
$A7+A22-A23-A20+A14+A1+A2+A11+A15+2^*A6-A12-A13+A3-2^*A4+2^*A5-T$	$A7+A22-A23-A20-A21+A14+A1+A2+A15+A6-A12-A13+A3-A4-A16$	A4	A9	A13	$2^*T+A16-2^*A7-2^*A22-A9+A23+2^*A20+A21-2^*A14-2^*A1-2^*A2-A11-2^*A15-3^*A6+2^*A12+A13-2^*A3+2^*A4-2^*A5$	A23	A35	L-T-A35
$A16+A20+A21-A14-A2+A17-A3$	$2^*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A10-A19-A14-A1-A2-A6-A3-A4-A5$	A5	A10	A14	A18	$A8-A16+A7+A22+A9+A19-A20-A21+A14+A1+2^*A2-A18+A6-A17+2^*A3+A4-T$	$7^*(L-T)/2-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35$	$5^*(T-L)/2+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35$
A25	$T+A25-A1-2^*A5+A13+A3+3^*A4-A6+2^*A12+A2-A18-A15+2^*A19+A14-A7+A23-2^*A17+A8-A31-L+A30$	A26	A27	A28	A29	$9^*(L-T)/2-A26-A27-A28-A29-2^*A25+2^*A5-A13-A3-3^*A4+A6-2^*A12-A2+A18+A15-2^*A19-A14+A1+A7-A23+2^*A17-A8+A31-A30$	$(L-T)/2$	4^*T-3^*L
L-T-A25	$2^*L-2^*T-A25+A1+2^*A5-A13-A3-3^*A4+A6-2^*A12-A2+A18+A15-2^*A19-A14+A7-A23+2^*A17-A8+A31-A30$	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	$7^*(T-L)/2+A26+A27+A28+A29+2^*A25-2^*A5+A13+A3+3^*A4-A6+2^*A12+A2-A18-A15+2^*A19+A14-A1-A7+A23-2^*A17+A8-A31+A30$	4^*T-3^*L	$(L-T)/2$

• Details

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The letters T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.11. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.10:

10a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								250
	-69	45	11	16	15	25	157	40	10	250
	41	124	12	17	21	-44	29	41	9	250
	112	-193	9	144	72	26	30	42	8	250
	50	-22	126	-34	22	27	31	43	7	250
	120	115	13	18	23	-121	32	44	6	250
	-119	-29	14	19	23	259	33	45	5	250
	65	160	15	20	24	28	-112	-80	130	250
	35	70	36	37	38	39	-80	25	50	250
	15	-20	14	13	12	11	130	50	25	250
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

10b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								271
	-80	45	11	16	15	25	179	40	20	271
	41	135	12	17	21	-44	29	41	19	271
	123	-215	9	166	72	26	30	42	18	271
	61	-22	137	-45	22	27	31	43	17	271
	131	115	13	18	34	-132	32	44	16	271
	-130	-29	14	19	23	281	33	45	15	271
	65	182	15	20	24	28	-123	-45	105	271
	35	60	36	37	38	39	-35	30	31	271
	25	0	24	23	22	21	95	31	30	271
	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 250$$

Second Example

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 211$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 271.$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 50 \times 175$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 60 \times 210.$$

5.1.4 Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 9

Result 5.11. *Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:*

L-A12-A4	$A6+A1+A13+A12+A14+A4+A5-2*L$	$2*L-A6-A1-A13-A14-A5$	$2*A19-A8-A6+L+A18-A11-A9+2*A17-A10-A4-A5+A2-A7$	$A7-2*A19+A8+A6-L-A18+A11+2*A9-2*A17+A10+A4+2*A5-A2$	L-A9-A5	$A19+A3+L-A12+A16-A15-A4-A8-A7$	$A7-A19+A8-A3-L+A13+A12-A16+A15+A4+A2$	L-A13-A2
A12+A4-A1	$3*L-A7-A6-A13-A12-A15-A14-A4-A5$	$A7+A6+A1+A13+A15+A14+A5-2*L$	$A7-2*A19+A8+2*A6+A11+A9-2*A17-A18+2*A10+A4+A5-L-A2$	$3*L-A7-A8-A6-A11-A9-A10-A4-A5$	$2*A19-A6-L+A18+2*A17-A10+A2$	$A7-A19+A8+A6-A3-L-A18+A12+A9-A16-A17+A15+A14+A10+A4+A5-A2$	$A19-A8-A6+3*L+A18-A11-A13-A12-A9+A16+A17-A15-A14-A10-A4-A5-A7$	A11+A13-L+A2+A3
A1	A7-A1+A15	L-A7-A15	L-A10-A6	$2*A19-L+A18-A9+2*A17-A5+A2$	$A6+L-A18+A9-2*A17+A10+A5-A2-2*A19$	$L-A6+A18-A9+A17-A14-A10-A5+A2$	$A6+A3-L-A18+A11+A9-A17+A14+A10+A5-A2$	L-A3-A11
$A7-2*A19+A8+A6-A18+A11+A9-A16-2*A17+A10+A4+A5-A2$	$2*A19-A8-A6+L+A18-A11-A9+A16+2*A17-A10-A4-A5-A7$	A2	$A7-A19-A3+A12-A16+A15+A4$	$A19-A6+A3+2*L-A1-A13-A12+A16+A17-A15-A14-A4-A5-A7$	$A6-L+A1+A13-A17+A14+A5$	A4	L-A4-A5	A5
$2*A19-A8-2*A6+L+2*A18-A11-2*A9+A16+3*A17-2*A10-A4-2*A5+2*A2-A7$	$A7-A19+A8+A6-L-A18+A11+A9-A16-A17+A10+A4+A5$	$A6+L-A18+A9-2*A17+A10+A5-2*A2-A19$	$A19+A3+A1+A18-A12+A16-A15-A4-A7$	$A7-A19+A6-L-A18+A13+A12-A16-A17+A15+A14+A4+A5$	$2*L-A6-A3-A1-A13+A17-A14-A5$	L-A4-A6	$A4+A6+A5+A7-L$	L-A5-A7
$A6-A18+A9-A17+A10+A5-A2$	L-A17-A19	$A19-A6+A18-A9+2*A17-A10-A5+A2$	L-A1-A18	A1+A18-A3	A3	A6	L-A6-A7	A7
A8	L-A8-A9	A9	A12	L-A12-A13	A13	A16	L-A16-A17	A17
L-A8-A10	$A8+A10+A9+A11-L$	L-A9-A11	L-A12-A14	$A12+A14+A13+A15-L$	L-A13-A15	L-A16-A18	$A16+A18+A17+A19-L$	L-A17-A19
A10	L-A10-A11	A11	A14	L-A14-A15	A15	A18	L-A18-A19	A19

• Details

It is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 with nine equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 9. The **semi-magic** squares of order 3 are based on the Result 2.2. See below two examples.

Example 5.12. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.11:

9x9	pan	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	9x9	pan	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441
600	164	-275	311	212	-178	166	172	-137	165	600	441	111	-169	205	159	-125	113	119	-84	112	441
600	25	444	-269	-176	460	-84	-145	476	-131	600	441	25	285	-163	-123	301	-31	-92	317	-78	441
600	11	31	158	164	-82	118	173	-139	166	600	441	11	31	105	111	-29	65	120	-86	113	441
600	-38	226	12	10	328	-138	14	171	15	600	441	-38	173	12	10	222	-85	14	118	15	441
600	235	-170	135	29	-154	325	170	-138	168	600	441	182	-117	82	29	-101	219	117	-85	115	441
600	3	144	53	161	26	13	16	167	17	600	441	3	91	53	108	26	13	16	114	17	441
600	18	163	19	22	155	23	26	147	27	600	441	18	110	19	22	102	23	26	94	27	441
600	162	-122	160	154	-106	152	146	-90	144	600	441	109	-69	107	101	-53	99	93	-37	91	441
	20	159	21	24	151	25	28	143	29	600		20	106	21	24	98	25	28	90	29	441
11a	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	11b	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$L_{Sm_{3 \times 3}} = 200$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 600$$

Second Example

$$L_{Sm_{3 \times 3}} = 147.$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 441.$$

5.2 Reduced Entries Semi-Magic Squares of Order 9

Based on the examples 2, 3 and 4 given in 5.2 we shall bring eight different ways to write **reduced entries semi-magic** squares of order 9. It is divided in two parts. The first is with magic square of order 3. The second part is with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5.

5.2.1 With Magic Square of Order 3

Result 5.12. *Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:*

$(L-S)/2-A29$	A30	$A21+A22+A23+A24-2*(L-S)$	$(L-S)/2-A21$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(L-S)/2-A23$	$(L-S)/2-A24$	$(7*S-3*L)/2-A15-A20-A30$	$A29+2*L-3*S+A15+A20$
A31	A29	$5*(L-S)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24$	A21	A22	A23	A24	$(5*S-3*L)/2-A29-A15-A20$	$A15+A20-A31$
$A25+A26+A27+A28-2*(L-S)$	$5*(L-S)/2-A25-A26-A27-A28$	A6	$M-A6-A9-A8+A7$	$S-M-A7$	A8	A9	$5*(L-S)/2-A16-A17-A18-A19$	$A16+A17+A18+A19-2*(L-S)$
$(L-S)/2-A25$	A25	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9+A5-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6$	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$
$(L-S)/2-A26$	A26	A5	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$S-M-A5$	A17	$(L-S)/2-A17$
$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	A4	A1	A2	$M-A1-A2$	$S-M-A4$	A18	$(L-S)/2-A18$
$(L-S)/2-A28$	A28	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	$S-M-A8$	$S-M-A6$	A19	$(L-S)/2-A19$
$(7*S-3*L)/2-A15-A31-A30$	$(5*S-3*L)/2-A15-A29-A30$	$5*(L-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	A11	A12	A13	A14	$(3*L-7*S)/2+A29+2*A15+A20+A30$	$A30-A20+A31$
$2*L-3*S+A29+A15+A30$	A15	$A11+A12+A13+A14-2*(L-S)$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(L-S)/2-A13$	$(L-S)/2-A14$	A20	$3*S-L-A29-2*A15-A20-A30$

• Details

It is **double-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 9 embedded with a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5. The four magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is **semi-magic** because of **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 in the middle. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have a condition $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$. The letters M, S and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.13. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 5.12:

1a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								160	1b	mgc	M/3=S/5								240	
	40	41	59	18	17	16	15	-1	15	220			41	29	38	37	36	35	-31	35	240	
	14	10	-9	32	33	34	35	35	36	220			50	41	32	33	34	35	35	36	240	
	79	-29	16	24	43	18	19	15	35	220			49	21	16	24	23	18	19	65	5	240
	13	37	94	3	28	29	-34	26	24	220			33	37	34	3	28	29	6	26	44	240
	12	38	15	46	20	-6	45	27	23	220			32	38	15	46	20	-6	25	27	43	240
	11	39	14	11	12	37	46	28	22	220			31	39	14	11	12	37	26	28	42	240
	10	40	-19	36	17	42	44	29	21	220			30	40	21	16	17	22	24	29	41	240
	16	25	35	21	22	23	24	30	24	220			56	25	85	21	22	23	24	30	-46	240
	25	19	15	29	28	27	26	31	20	220			45	-51	-15	49	48	47	46	31	40	240
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220			240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{Sm_{5 \times 5}} = 120$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 220$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 100$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 240$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 50 \times 125$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 70 \times 175$$

Result 5.13. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

L-T-A31	$T-L-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24
L-T-A24	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	A24
L-T-A25	A13	A12	$3*(T-S)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A25
L-T-A26	$A15+A16-(T-S)/4$	$3*(T-S)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-S/3$	$2*S/3-A2$	$2*S/3-A1$	$3*(T-S)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-S)/4$	A26
L-T-A27	$(T-S)/2-A15$	A15	$4*S/3-2*A1-A2$	$S/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*S/3$	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A27
L-T-A28	$(T-S)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2$	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	A28
L-T-A29	$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-S)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*S-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A29
L-T-A30	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A4$	$(T-S)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*S-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A30
$8*T-7*L+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	$2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 9 embedded with a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7. The four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is **semi-magic** because of **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The letters M, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.14. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.13:

2a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								420	2b	mgc	T/7=L/9								261
	-101	503	79	83	87	91	95	99	-706	230		-73	475	79	83	87	91	95	99	-675	261
	-73	15	63	63	23	19	43	-26	103	230		-45	15	63	63	23	19	43	-23	103	261
	-77	59	55	7	47	51	96	-115	107	230		-49	59	55	7	47	51	93	-109	107	261
	-81	103	-33	6	25	29	31	39	111	230		-53	103	-33	5	27	31	31	39	111	261
	-85	3	67	43	20	-3	35	35	115	230		-57	3	67	47	21	-5	35	35	115	261
	-89	-1	71	11	15	34	39	31	119	230		-61	-1	71	11	15	37	39	31	119	261
	-93	75	124	55	23	27	-135	31	123	230		-65	75	121	55	23	27	-129	31	123	261
	-97	-54	-147	15	47	43	91	205	127	230		-69	-51	-141	15	47	43	91	199	127	261
	926	-473	-49	-53	-57	-61	-65	-69	131	230		733	-417	-21	-25	-29	-33	-37	-41	131	261
	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230		261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 230$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 63$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 203$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 261.$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 70 \times 105$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 70 \times 105.$$

Result 5.14. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

L-T-A29	$T-A_{21}-A_{20}-A_{19}-A_{18}-A_{17}-A_{16}-L+2*A_{29}+A_{28}+A_{27}+A_{26}+A_{25}+A_{24}+A_{23}+A_{22}$	A16	A17	A18	A19	A20	A21	L-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22
L-T-A22	$A_1+A_2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A_2$	$2*M/3-A_1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A_5-A_6$	$A_5+A_6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11	A22
L-T-A23	$4*M/3-2*A_1-A_2$	M/3	$2*A_1+A_2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A23
L-T-A24	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A24
L-T-A25	$A_4-A_1-A_2+2*A_5+A_6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A_1+2*(S-M)-2*A_4+A_2-2*A_5-A_6$	(S-M)/2	2*M-S	$5*(T-S)/2-A_{11}-A_{12}-A_{13}-A_{14}$	$3*(S-T)/2+A_{11}+A_{12}+A_{13}+A_{14}$	A25
L-T-A26	$A_1+3*(S-M)/2+A_2-2*A_5-A_6-A_4$	S-M-A4	$2*A_4-S+M-A_1-A_2+2*A_5+A_6$	2*M-S	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	A26
L-T-A27	$T-3*S/2-M/2+A_8+2*A_4-A_1-A_2+2*A_5+A_{12}-A_{11}$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A_8-2*A_4+A_1+A_2-2*A_5-A_{12}+A_{11}-A_9-A_{10}$	A10	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A27
L-T-A28	$S/2+M/2-A_8-2*A_4+A_1+A_2-2*A_5-A_{12}+A_{11}$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A_8+2*A_4-A_1-A_2+2*A_5+A_{12}-A_{11}+A_9+A_{10}-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A28
$8*T+A_{29}+A_{28}+A_{27}+A_{26}+A_{25}+A_{24}+A_{23}+A_{22}-7*L$	$2*L-2*T+A_{21}+A_{20}+A_{19}+A_{18}+A_{17}+A_{16}-2*A_{29}-A_{28}-A_{27}-A_{26}-A_{25}-A_{24}-A_{23}-A_{22}$	L-T-A16	L-T-A17	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	A29

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 7. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 , 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length in each case. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is **semi-magic** because of **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The letters M, S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.15. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.14:

3a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								150	3b	mgc	T/7=L/9								288
	19	98	28	29	30	31	32	33	-70	230		23	94	28	29	30	31	32	33	-12	288
	26	3	28	29	44	6	21	39	34	230		30	3	28	29	44	6	21	93	34	288
	25	46	20	-6	15	35	22	38	35	230		29	46	20	-6	15	35	22	92	35	288
	24	11	12	37	16	34	23	37	36	230		28	11	12	37	16	34	23	91	36	288
	23	12	14	49	25	10	60	0	37	230		27	12	14	49	25	10	195	-81	37	288
	22	38	36	1	10	25	24	36	38	230		26	38	36	1	10	25	24	90	38	288
	21	29	18	19	64	20	30	-10	39	230		25	83	18	19	145	20	57	-118	39	288
	20	31	42	41	-4	40	-10	30	40	230		24	31	96	95	-31	94	-118	57	40	288
	50	-38	32	31	30	29	28	27	41	230		76	-30	36	35	34	33	32	31	41	288
	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230		288	288	288	288	288	288	288	288	288	288

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 170$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 230$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 224$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 288$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 50 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 60 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 50 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 114 \times 285$$

Result 5.15. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

L-T-A32	T-A24-A23-A22- A21-A20-A19- L+2*A32+A31+A30 +A29+A28+A27+ A26+A25	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	L-A32-A31- A30-A29-A28- A27-A26-A25
L-T-A25	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	A14	T-S-A14	A25
L-T-A26	3*S-4*M-A6+A9- 2*A7-A8+A2+A1- A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M- 2*S+A4+2*A7+A 8-A2-A1-A9+A6	A15	T-S-A15	A26
L-T-A27	2*A7+A8-A2-A1	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-2*A7- A8+A2+A1	(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A17- A16-A15-A14	(3/2)*S- (3/2)*T+A14+A15 +A16+A17	A27
L-T-A28	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16	A28
L-T-A29	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S- 2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17	A29
L-T-A30	T-S-A7+A11- A8+A15-A14	A11	A7+A8+(3/2)*T- A13-A12-2*A11- A15+A14-(3/2)*S	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A30
L-T-A31	A7-A11+A8- A15+A14	T-S-A11	(1/2)*S+A13+A12+ 2*A11-A7-A8+A15- A14-(1/2)*T	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A31
8*T+A32+A31 +A30+A29+A 28+A27+A26 +A25-7*L	2*L-2*T+A24+ A23+A22+A21+ A20+A19-2*A32- A31-A30-A29-A28- A27-A26-A25	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	A32

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 7. It again contains a **single-digit bordered semi-magic** of order 5 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is **semi-magic** because of **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The **single-digit bordered** of order 5 is also **semi-magic**, but it don't make any effect on the magic sum of order 9. The letters M, S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.16. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.15:

4a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								420	4b	mgc	S/5=T/7								279
	-2	121	29	30	31	32	33	34	-48	260		20	99	29	30	31	32	33	34	-29	279
	5	16	54	33	18	19	24	56	35	260		27	16	54	34	18	19	24	52	35	279
	4	20	-7	48	49	30	25	55	36	260		26	23	-7	48	49	28	25	51	36	279
	3	29	86	30	-26	21	98	-18	37	260		25	29	86	30	-26	22	88	-12	37	279
	2	14	11	12	67	36	26	54	38	260		24	14	11	12	67	37	26	50	38	279
	1	61	-4	17	32	34	27	53	39	260		23	59	-3	17	33	35	27	49	39	279
	0	67	21	67	22	23	40	-20	40	260		22	63	21	61	22	23	38	-11	40	279
	-1	13	59	13	58	57	-20	40	41	260		21	13	55	15	54	53	-11	38	41	279
	248	-81	11	10	9	8	7	6	42	260		91	-37	33	32	31	30	29	28	42	279
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260		279	279	279	279	279	279	279	279	279	279

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 220$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 260$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 141$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 217$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 279$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 80 \times 200$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 76 \times 190$$

Result 5.16. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

L-T-A31	$T-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18-L+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24
L-T-A24	A15	$T-S+A8+A12-A11$	A8	$S-A15-A16-A10-A9-2*A8-A12+A11$	A9	A10	A16	A24
L-T-A25	$5*T-6*S-A15+A16-A14-A12-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$5*S-4*T+A11+A12+A13+A14-A16+A15$	A25
L-T-A26	A12	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	T-S-A12	A26
L-T-A27	A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13	A27
L-T-A28	A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	$2*M-S$	T-S-A14	A28
L-T-A29	A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	(S-M)/2	T-S-A11	A29
L-T-A30	$6*S-A16-4*T$	A11-A8-A12	T-S-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+2*A8+T-2*S+A12-A11$	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15	A30
$8*T+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-7*L$	$2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 5. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is **semi-magic** because of **single-digit bordered** magic squares of orders 9 and 7. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have two conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ and $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$. The letters M, S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.17. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.16:

5a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								240	5b	mgc									225
	9	108	28	29	30	31	32	33	-100	200		9	108	28	29	30	31	32	33	-75	225
	16	25	49	18	-7	19	20	26	34	200		16	25	69	18	-2	19	20	26	34	225
	15	-59	-7	48	49	14	16	89	35	200		15	36	-8	50	51	17	15	14	35	225
	14	22	86	30	-26	15	15	8	36	200		14	22	90	31	-28	15	17	28	36	225
	13	23	11	12	67	16	14	7	37	200		13	23	11	12	70	16	16	27	37	225
	12	24	22	14	9	15	60	6	38	200		12	24	21	14	13	16	61	26	38	225
	11	21	8	16	21	60	15	9	39	200		11	21	11	18	19	61	16	29	39	225
	10	94	-19	12	37	11	10	5	40	200		10	24	-19	32	52	31	30	25	40	225
	100	-58	22	21	20	19	18	17	41	200		125	-58	22	21	20	19	18	17	41	225
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ and $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 150$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 260$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 93$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 125$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 175$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 225$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 30 \times 45$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 32 \times 48$$

Result 5.17. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

L-T-A28	T-L-A34-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29+2*A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	L-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21
L-T-A21	A18	T-S+A11+A15-A14	A11	S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	A19	A21
L-T-A22	5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18	A22
L-T-A23	A15	3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6	T-S-A15	A23
L-T-A24	A16	A5	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-A5	T-S-A16	A24
L-T-A25	A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	T-S-A17	A25
L-T-A26	A14	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	T-S-A14	A26
L-T-A27	6*S-A19-4*T	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	A18+A19+A13+A12+ 2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A27
8*T-7*L+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21	2*L-2*T+A34+A33+A32+A31+A30+A29-2*A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	A28

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 9 embedded with a magic square of order 3. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is **semi-magic** because of **single-digit bordered** magic squares of orders 9, 7 and 5. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have three conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$, $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$ and $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$. The letters M, S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.18. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.17:

6a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								450	6b	mgc	M/3=S/5=T/7=L/9								243
	-8	55	49	50	51	52	53	54	-136	220		6	41	49	50	51	52	53	54	-113	243
	-1	38	62	31	-55	32	33	39	41	220		13	38	86	31	-70	32	33	39	41	243
	-2	-141	26	34	33	28	29	171	42	220		12	-6	26	25	27	28	29	60	42	243
	-3	35	44	13	38	39	16	-5	43	220		11	35	35	16	32	33	19	19	43	243
	-4	36	25	56	30	4	35	-6	44	220		10	36	25	44	27	10	29	18	44	243
	-5	37	24	21	22	47	36	-7	45	220		9	37	24	21	22	38	30	17	45	243
	-6	34	31	26	27	32	34	-4	46	220		8	34	25	29	27	26	28	20	46	243
	-7	141	-32	-1	85	-2	-3	-8	47	220		7	15	-32	23	124	22	21	16	47	243
	256	-15	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	48	220		167	13	5	4	3	2	1	0	48	243
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$, $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$ and $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{Sm_{5 \times 5}} = 150$$

$$T_{Sm_{7 \times 7}} = 180$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 220$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 81$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 135$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 189$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 243$$

5.2.2 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

Result 5.18. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

L-T-A31	T-A23-A22-A21-A20- A19-A18-L+2*A31 +A30+A29+A28+A27 +A26+A25+A24	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29- A28-A27-A26- A25-A24
L-T-A24	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	A24
L-T-A25	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5- A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	A25
L-T-A26	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6- A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15- A14-A13	3*(S-T)/2+A13+ A14+A15+A16	A26
L-T-A27	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15	A27
L-T-A28	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	A28
L-T-A29	T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14- A13	A10	A7+A8+3*T/2-A12- A11-2*A10-A14+A13- 3*S/2	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A29
L-T-A30	A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	S/2+A12+A11+2*A1 0-A7-A8+A14-A13- T/2	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A30
8*T+A31+A30+A29 +A28+A27+A26+ A25+A24-7*L	2*L-2*T+A23+A22 +A21+A20+A19+A18- 2*A31-A30-A29-A28- A27-A26-A25-A24	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 7. It contains **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. It is **semi-magic** because of **single-digit bordered** magic squares of order 9. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The letters S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.19. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.18:

7a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								300	7b	mgc	T/7=L/9								225
	-45	340	56	59	62	65	68	71	-426	250		-45	340	56	59	62	65	68	71	-451	225
	-24	5	8	102	11	14	41	19	74	250		-24	5	8	103	11	14	41	-7	74	225
	-27	41	17	-22	20	84	44	16	77	250		-27	41	17	-22	20	85	44	-10	77	225
	-30	-7	96	23	47	-19	-32	92	80	250		-30	-7	97	23	47	-19	-97	131	80	225
	-33	29	11	-4	69	35	47	13	83	250		-33	29	11	-4	70	35	47	-13	83	225
	-36	72	8	41	-7	26	50	10	86	250		-36	73	8	41	-7	26	50	-16	86	225
	-39	46	32	-1	35	38	30	20	89	250		-39	20	32	-40	35	38	17	73	89	225
	-42	14	28	61	25	22	20	30	92	250		-42	14	2	74	-1	-4	73	17	92	225
	526	-290	-6	-9	-12	-15	-18	-21	95	250		501	-290	-6	-9	-12	-15	-18	-21	95	225
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250		225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 250$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 141$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 175$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 225$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 60 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 34 \times 85$$

Result 5.19. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

L-T-A33	T-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20-L+2*A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	A25	L-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26
L-T-A26	A17	T-S+A10+A14-A13	A10	S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	A18	A26
L-T-A27	A14	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	T-S-A14	A27
L-T-A28	5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	5*S-4*T+A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17	A28
L-T-A29	A15	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	T-S-A15	A29
L-T-A30	A16	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	T-S-A16	A30
L-T-A31	A13	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	T-S-A13	A31
L-T-A32	6*S-A18-4*T	A13-A10-A14	T-S-A10	A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+T-2*S+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	A32
8*T+A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26-7*L	2*L-2*T+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20-2*A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	A33

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 9 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. It is **semi-magic** because of **single-digit bordered** magic squares of orders 9 and 7. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must two conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ and $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$. The letters S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

5.2.3 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 7

Result 5.20. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 9:

L-T-A38	T-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-L+2*A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31	A25	A26	A27	A28	A29	A30	L-A38-A37-A36-A35-A34-A33-A32-A31
L-T-A31	A7+A22+A9+A10+A14+A1+A2+A6+A3+A5-A12-T-A16	A8+A23+A19-A1-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+A4-A5	A1	A6	A22-A10+A19+A2-A18-A13+A3	A15	2*T-A8+A16-A7-2*A22-A9-A23-2*A19-A14-A1-2*A2+A18-A6+A17-2*A3-A4	A31
L-T-A32	A19+A14+A2-A18-A17+A12+A3+2*A4-A5-A7	T+A16-A7-A22-A19+A20-A14-A1-2*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A3	A2	A7	A11	A7+A22-A19-A20+A1+A6-A12-2*A4+A5-A16	A19	A32
L-T-A33	T-A9-A10+A23-A14-A1-A15-A6+A12-A3-A5	2*A7+2*A22+A9+A19-A20+A14+2*A1+2*A2+A11-A18+A15+2*A6-A12-A13+2*A3-A4+2*A5-2*T-A16	A14+A11+A15+A6-A4-A23-A20	2*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A23-2*A19-A14-2*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A12-A3-A4	A8-A7-A22+A9+A10+A23+A19+A20-A1-A11-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+3*A4-A5	A16	A20	A33
L-T-A34	T-A22-A23-A19-A20-A21-A2+A18+A15-A12-A4	A10-A23-A19+A1+A6-A12+A5	T+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-A6-A3-A5	A22-A10+A23+2*A19+A14+2*A2+A11-A18-A17+A12+A3+A4-T	A12	A17	A21	A34
L-T-A35	T-A7-A22+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-2*A6+A12+A13-A3+A4-A5	A16-A7-A22+A23+A19+A20+A21-A1-A15-A6+2*A12+A13-A3+2*A4-A5	A3	A8	T-A8+A7-A9-A23-2*A19-A20-A14+A1-A2+A18+A15+A6+A17-2*A12-A13-A3-3*A4+A5	A7+A22+A9-A23+A19-A20-A21+2*A14+A1+2*A2+A11-A18+A15+2*A6-A17-A12-A13+2*A3+A5-T-A16	A22	A35
L-T-A36	A7+A22-A23-A20+A14+A1+A2+A11+A15+2*A6-A12-A13+A3-2*A4+2*A5-T	A7+A22-A23-A20-A21+A14+A1+A2+A15+A6-A12-A13+A3-A4-A16	A4	A9	A13	2*T+A16-2*A7-2*A22-A9+A23+2*A20+A21-2*A14-2*A1-2*A2-A11-2*A15-3*A6+2*A12+A13-2*A3+2*A4-2*A5	A23	A36
L-T-A37	A16+A20+A21-A14-A2+A17-A3	2*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A10-A19-A14-A1-A2-A6-A3-A4-A5	A5	A10	A14	A18	A8-A16+A7+A22+A9+A19-A20-A21+A14+A1+2*A2-A18+A6-A17+2*A3+A4-T	A37
8*T+A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31-7*L	2*L-2*T+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25-2*A38-A37-A36-A35-A34-A33-A32-A31	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	A38

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered semi-magic** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 in the middle. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must apply a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The letters T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 5.20. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.20:

9a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								300	9b	mgc	T/7=L/9								270
	2	129	35	36	37	38	39	40	-106	250		12	119	35	36	37	38	39	40	-86	270
	9	-69	45	11	16	15	25	157	41	250		19	-79	45	11	16	15	25	177	41	270
	8	41	124	12	17	21	-44	29	42	250		18	41	134	12	17	21	-44	29	42	270
	7	112	-193	9	144	72	26	30	43	250		17	122	-213	9	164	72	26	30	43	270
	6	50	-22	126	-34	22	27	31	44	250		16	60	-22	136	-44	22	27	31	44	270
	5	120	115	13	18	23	-121	32	45	250		15	130	115	13	18	33	-131	32	45	270
	4	-119	-29	14	19	23	259	33	46	250		14	-129	-29	14	19	23	279	33	46	270
	3	65	160	15	20	24	28	-112	47	250		13	65	180	15	20	24	28	-122	47	270
	206	-79	15	14	13	12	11	10	48	250		146	-59	25	24	23	22	21	20	48	270
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250		270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 250$$

Second Example

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 210$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 270.$$

6 Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author’s contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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